

Talking Charts - Research Data Management Plan

Kathleen Gregory and Laura Koesten

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This research data management plan (RDMP) describes how data is handled in the [Talking Charts](#) research project. The core project team consists of Laura Koesten (PI), Kathleen Gregory (co-PI), Torsten Moeller (co-PI), and Sarah Davies (special advisor) and two PhD researchers. The project is funded by the [Vienna Science and Technology Fund \(WWTF\)](#) and the City of Vienna through project ICT20-065.

The project uses mixed methods drawn from computer science, science and technology studies and the social sciences. This RDMP is adapted from the data management plan used in the [Meaningful Data Counts](#) research project (Morisette et al, 2020), and is based on a template created for the [Portage Network](#). This RDMP is in compliance with the [Research Data Management Policy](#) of the University of Vienna, which also recommends the Portage guidelines for creating data management plans. The RDMP is a living document that is expected to be revised as the Talking Charts project evolves.

The RDMP consists of the answers (labeled A1, A2, etc) to the questions in the Portage Network template. A complete version, including the questions and guidelines listed in the template, is available [via this link](#).

Responsibilities and Resources

A1. The PI and Co-PIs will ultimately be responsible for all research data. They will set up necessary infrastructure and make sure that all team members are aware of individual responsibilities from the beginning of the project. Although the main responsibility rests with the PI and Co-PI, every team member, particularly lead authors, will be responsible for proper documentation, versioning, storage and publication of research data as part of their usual workflows.

A2. Should the PI leave the project, the co-PIs will share responsibility. Should a co-PI leave the project, the PI and/or remaining co-PI will assume responsibility. Responsibilities will be conferred to (in order) 1 – PI, 2 – Co-PI Gregory, 3 –co-PI Moeller, 4- one of the two PhD researchers on the project.

A3. The project is funded by the WWTF for a total of EUR 390,577 over a 3-year period. Using [TU Delft's Data Management Costing Tool](#), we estimate that our RDM costs amount to .2 FTE.

Data Collection

A4. We will be conducting both quantitative and qualitative research. Our methods include the qualitative and quantitative analysis of existing charts in academic journals and popular science news sources, online questionnaires/surveys, semi-structured interviews, and ethnographic field notes.

The project will collect the following types of data, which are listed according to envisioned studies.

- Analysis of popular science magazines (i.e. Scientific American)
 - Charts and articles from scholarly and popular science publications (PDFs)
 - Spreadsheets/documents with links and bibliographic references (CSV)
 - These charts and articles will be stored during the project in shared folders on Google Drive to facilitate access for collaborators who do not work at the University. Only team members and collaborators will have access to these folders.
 - At the completion of the project, this data will be moved to the University's cloud storage and deleted from Google Drive.

- Dataset of charts
 - Spreadsheets with bibliographic information (CSV)
 - Images of charts (PDFs, or other open image format, ie. png)
 - Data will be stored on one of the university's cloud storage options. The exact option will be determined by the size of the dataset which we are able to create.
 - If copyright restrictions and size limitations allow, the dataset will be made openly available on Zenodo, along with our other published data.

- Interview recordings and transcripts
 - Interviews will be audio- or video-recorded using the internal functionalities of video-conferencing systems, i.e. Zoom.
 - Recordings will be exported from Zoom and stored in an open format (mp4) in the cloud storage of the University in a folder with restricted

access permissions for active team members. Recordings will be immediately deleted from online platforms (i.e. Zoom) and will be permanently deleted from the secure cloud storage at the end of the research project.

- Interview recordings will be transcribed and anonymized. Participant numbers will be assigned to each interview. Transcripts will be stored on the cloud storage of the university.
 - Codebooks linking participants with participant IDs will be stored in a separate folder on the University cloud storage and will be accessible only to researchers who are conducting the study.
 - All interview transcripts will include a summary including identity of data collector, location of interview and the interview date.
- Questionnaire data from online diary study
 - Questionnaires will be sent to researchers using a survey software licensed by the university, i.e. EvaSys or limesurvey.
 - The collected data will be available in CSV format after anonymization.

A5 – A: Our data will be collected in the following file formats:

- CSV (all numerical and categorical data)
- PDF and TXT (interview transcripts)
- Images and articles (PDFs or pngs)
- Video/audio recording files (mp4)
- atlas.ti or NVivo format (coded interview transcripts)

A5 – B: We will make sure that all published data will be available in non-proprietary formats, such as CSV, that are easily shared with and reused by other researchers.

A6 – A: All data will be organized via pre-determined file structure, file naming convention and version control, and will include a ReadMe file as the guiding internal document to document collection and cleaning. We will follow a general agreed-upon file naming convention, as shown below:

- Unprocessed data collected from an instrument (e.g., questionnaire results, interview recording): stored on a secure server, namely the cloud storage instance of the Visualization and Data Analysis research group (Computer Science Faculty) at the University of Vienna.

*File naming: Content_Unprocessed_v1.csv (e.g.,
OnlineDiaryStudy_Unprocessed_v1.csv)*

→ Processed data (data that has been processed, e.g., anonymized interview transcript): stored on the University's internal cloud storage.

File naming: Content_Processed_v1.txt (e.g., ExpertInterview1_Processed.pdf)

→ Cleaned data (processed data that has been corrected, enriched and analyzed, e.g., anonymized questionnaire results with incomplete cases removed): stored on the University's internal cloud storage.

There might be multiple versions of cleaned data. For every major data cleaning step, we will create a new file version (e.g., v1, v2).

File naming: Content_Cleaned_v1.csv (e.g., OnlineDiaryStudy_Cleaned_v4.csv)

→ Final data (cleaned data with documentation): The final data is the final version of the cleaned data plus documentation, such as the ReadMe file, to ensure reuse by others. This version will be published on Zenodo, where it will be archived and downloadable for a minimum of 20 years.

File naming: Content_Published.csv and Content_ReadMe.txt (e.g., OnlineDiaryStudy_Published.csv and DiaryStudy_ReadMe.txt)

A6 – B: We will follow the following general workflow:

1. Data collection
 1. Collect data via instrument (e.g., questionnaire, interview protocol, API)
 2. Document data collection methods in ReadMe file for each data collection method.
2. Data storage and preprocessing
 1. Store unprocessed data on secure cloud server provided by the University.
 2. If data contains personally identifiable information, anonymize and deidentify
 3. Document preprocessing procedures in ReadMe file
 4. Store anonymized and de-identified data in cloud storage provided by the university.
 5. Permanent file removal of unprocessed data (e.g., audio/video recordings) at the end of the relevant study.

3. Data cleaning
 1. Clean and prepare data for analysis
 2. Document data cleaning procedures in ReadMe file
4. Analysis
 1. Analyze data
 2. Document methods of analysis in ReadMe file for internal use
5. Publication
 1. Publish data or codebooks and interview protocols and relevant ReadMe files on Zenodo

A6 – C: When joining the project team, all collaborators will get access to the shared Google Drive folder, the shared cloud storage and be trained on using this RDMP via an onboarding document. Onboarding will describe workflows, data storage practices, file naming conventions and RDM responsibilities of each team member.

Documentation and Metadata

A7. Every dataset will be accompanied by a ReadMe file that will serve as an internal log to document data collection, processing and cleaning procedures as well as methods of analysis (see Q6). This will serve as the basis for a ReadMe file which we will publish with shared data; this shared ReadMe will include a data dictionary that outlines the codes and variables we use in, e.g., online questionnaires. All qualitative interviews will include a summary including identity of data collector, location of interview and the interview date.

A8. In order to encourage the reuse of data, methods, results, and to gain early feedback and improve quality, the project adheres to the principles of open science. One of our research goals is to share data and results as early as possible in the research project. This will be achieved by publicly documenting the project's progress by publishing outputs on the project's Zenodo community page. Every team member will be held responsible to continuously document any major processing, updating and analysis of the data in the relevant ReadMe files. Their responsibilities will be highlighted in an onboarding document that each new team member will be expected to read.

While every team member is responsible for documentation as part of the everyday workflow, the lead author or leading researcher on the team who works on data collection and analysis will be responsible to ensure that documentation is sufficient and ReadMe files are complete before the dataset is published. We are using the [CRedit taxonomy](#) and follow the project's authorship guidelines to determine authorship roles and responsibilities at the beginning of each project

A9. Each dataset will be published using the [Datacite Metadata Schema 4.3](#) (or later).

A10. We will ensure transparency through documentation in ReadMe files. Details are provided in A6-8 and A16.

Storage and Backup

A11. Our exact storage needs will depend in large part on the development of our various study approaches (i.e. the number of charts and images which we can collect, or the number of expert interviews which we conduct) as well as technical and legal feasibility. The University offers secure cloud storage solutions for varying sizes of data.

A12 & A13. All data will be stored on the University cloud storage, with the exception of image and article data which are shared during the project with external collaborators. These data will be shared in a restricted access Google Drive folder. Files stored on Google Drive are automatically synced between different platforms and users, and are version controlled in case older versions need to be restored. Personal data from interviews and surveys will be stored on secure servers accessible to the PI, Co-PIs and team members directly involved in data collection and interview transcription via nextcloud. The PI and Co-PIs will have permanent access to the university cloud storage, while team members involved in data collection and transcription will only have temporary access to perform anonymization or transcription. Data will be anonymized and de-identified immediately to store anonymized versions of the data in a separate folder on the cloud storage solution, to which all team members have access. All data will be accessible to team members and collaborators until five years after the end of the project, except for the interview recordings which will be deleted at the end of the study from the secure storage.

Data Sharing and Reuse

A14 – A: Outputs of the project will be in long-term storage via deposit in Zenodo (up to 20 years). We do not anticipate the need for preservation measures beyond this timeframe. All final processed and cleaned datasets as well as select working documents will be published on Zenodo using a CC-BY license to ensure maximum diffusion and reuse. Each Zenodo document will be issued a DOI, which we will use, when citing documents and datasets in related publications.

Unprocessed data will not be published, however, protocols for data collection, processing and cleaning secondary data sources will be documented in README files. As mentioned above, raw data for interviews will be permanently deleted.

[Zenodo will retain uploaded items](#) for the lifetime of the repository, which equals the lifetime of the host laboratory [CERN](#) which is currently financed for a minimum of 20 years. In case of closure of the repository, CERN has committed its best efforts to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

A15. We will publish final (de-identified, processed, cleaned and analyzed) data in on Zenodo, where each dataset receives a DOI to increase findability and reuse. When possible, we will publish software code (i.e. using Jupyter Notebooks or on GitHub) to ensure transparent and open methodology including data collection, processing and analysis. We will publish interview protocols, codebooks and data documentation as PDFs in Zenodo. We will not publish interview transcripts in order to avoid potential identification of participants, which may happen despite our de-identification workflows.

A16. We aim to make final data and publications open access, using a CC-BY license wherever possible. By default our data and publications will be shared using [Creative Commons Attribution CC-BY 4.0 International](#) license. If CC-BY is not possible, we will use [CC-BY ND](#).

A17. Our aim is to promote knowledge mobilization as much as possible using traditional publication venues as well as social media. All published datasets and this RDMP, as well as presentation slides will be aggregated on the project's [Zenodo community page](#) so they are accessible from one location. Preprints will be published on the [arxiv preprint server](#). The Zenodo community page will also be linked to the [project website](#).

All publications will properly cite underlying datasets by listing their metadata and DOI (according to [Datacite Metadata Schema 4.3](#)) in the reference list to allow readers to access and reuse the dataset. We will frequently announce publication of outputs via the PI and Co-PIs' social media accounts. Internally, research outputs will be communicated through Slack channels.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

A18. The project will comply with the research data management policies of its host institutions, which take into account relevant legislation, industry standards and best

practices. Specifically, we'll be referring primarily to the University of Vienna's [Research Data Management Policy](#) and the EU's General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#)).

A19. We will store sensitive data on the secure university cloud service provided by the Computer Science Faculty at the University of Vienna. Access to the secure location will be limited to the PI and Co-PIs for the entire project. Additional team members will be granted access for the time that they are working on data collection and anonymization of sensitive data. (Also see answers to question 13 and 15).

Collection of qualitative and personal data will proceed following formal best practices for ethical research and will require explicit and informed participant agreement for data sharing following the [Recommended Recommended Informed Consent Language for Data Sharing](#) (ICPSR). Datasets will be stored securely with password protection and encryption when assessed as sensitive. Data will be anonymized in reporting, except where explicitly agreed otherwise.

References

Morissette, Erica, Harper, Lina, Peters, Isabella, Tayler, Felicity, & Haustein, Stefanie. (2020). Research Data Management Plan for the Meaningful Data Counts Project (v.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4092122>